

Data Management Plan for project "Analysis of the Applicability of Artificial Intelligence Methods in the Field of European Union Fund Projects"

Version 2

Description

This plan outlines the data used in the project "Analysis of the Applicability of Artificial Intelligence Methods in the Field of European Union Fund Projects" (project ID: VPP – Mākslīgais intelekts – 2024/1-0003), which is funded by the Latvian Council of Science.

Funder

Latvian Council of Science

Grant

VPP- Mākslīgais
intelekts-2024/1-0003

Researchers

Raivis Skadiņš (0000-0003-0929-2380)

Organizations
University of Latvia

1. Main Info

Title of DMP: Data Management Plan for project "Analysis of the Applicability of Artificial Intelligence Methods in the Field of European Union Fund Projects"

Description:

This plan outlines the data used in the project "Analysis of the Applicability of Artificial Intelligence Methods in the Field of European Union Fund Projects" (project ID: VPP – Mākslīgais intelekts – 2024/1-0003), which is funded by the Latvian Council of Science.

Researchers:

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Organizations:

University of Latvia

Contact: Skadiņš Raivis (raivis.skadins@lu.lv)

2. Funding

Funding organizations: Latvian Council of Science

Grants: VPP- Mākslīgais intelekts-2024/1-0003

Project:

3. License

License: CC-BY-4.0

Access Rights: Public

Publication Date: 2025-02-27

4. Templates

Descriptions

CFCA example documents

This dataset has been prepared by the Central Finance and Contracting Agency (CFCA) to provide researchers with insights into CFCA processes related to the monitoring, analysis, and processing of complex project management data. The dataset is stored in CFCA's information system, KPVIS. Due to the sensitive nature of the data, it is not publicly accessible.

Template: [LCS FARP](#)

Type: [Dataset](#)

1 Data Summary

1.1 Data Summary

1.1.1 What is the purpose of the data collection/generation?

This dataset, prepared by the Central Finance and Contracting Agency (CFCA), is designed to support research on CFCA's processes for monitoring, analyzing, and managing complex project data. It provides valuable insights into how CFCA oversees project implementation and evaluates performance.

1.1.2 Type of data generated/collected

Textual data

1.1.3 Format of data generated/collected

- HTML
- PDF
- XLS
- Others

Microsoft Word

1.1.4 Expected size of the data – give expected size and choose unit of measurement

50

MB

1.1.5 Are you re-using this data set?

No

1.1.6 If No, please describe, if you have considered re-using any of existing data?

This dataset is specific to CFCA and contains sensitive information. It has not been previously published and has been created exclusively for this project.

1.1.8 To whom the data might be useful ("data utility")? Other relevant remarks)

Just for the goals of this project

2 Research Data Management

2.1 Metadata and documentation

2.1.1 Will data be attributed with standard identification mechanism (e.g. persistent and unique identifiers such as Digital Object Identifiers – DOI)?

No

2.1.2 Do you plan to provide metadata for your data?

Yes

2.1.3 Will you use any metadata standard?

Yes

Dublin Core

2.1.4 Will search keywords be provided that optimize possibilities for re-use?

No

2.1.5 Will you follow any naming conventions for keywords?

No

2.1.6 Will you provide clear version numbers?

Yes

2.2 Making data openly accessible

2.2.1 What type of access the data generated/produced will have (choose one)?

restricted, no access (access is denied, files will be opened only through contact person to the authors)

The dataset is stored in CFCA's information system, KPVIS. Due to the sensitive nature of the data, it is not publicly accessible.

2.2.2 Will you apply embargo period to access for your data?

No

2.2.3 Will data, associated metadata, documentation and code be made accessible with means of a repository?

No

Data will be stored in CFCA's information system KPVIS.

2.2.4 What methods or software tools are needed to access the data?

CFCA's information system KPVIS

2.2.5 Will documentation about the software needed to access the data included?

No

2.2.6 Is it possible to include the relevant software (e.g. in open source code)?

No

2.3 Making data interoperable

2.3.1 Are the formats open to software applications and to recombination with different data sets?

No

2.3.2 Will you use data standard vocabulary/taxonomy to make your data interoperable?

No

2.4 Increase data re-use

2.4.2 Are the data usable by third parties, in particular after the end of the project?

No

2.4.4 How long is it intended that the data remains re-usable?

2025-08-27

2.4.5 Are data quality assurance processes provided?

No

3 Resources and Security

3.1 Allocation of resources

3.1.1 How will costs be covered for making data FAIR during project realization?

Data will be created by CFCA, as their contribution to the project.

3.2 Data security

3.2.1 What security measures will be used for data security?

Data is stored in CFCA's information system KPVIS, which provides user authentication and authorization.

3.3 Ethical aspects

3.3.1 Are there any ethical or legal issues that could have an impact on data collection and sharing?

No

3.3.2 Have you got/will you get permission from ethics committee to collect and process data (if applicable)?

No

3.3.3 Is informed consent for data sharing and long term preservation included in questionnaires dealing with personal data, if applicable?

No

3.3.4 Will data collected/generated include personal data/ sensitive information?

Yes

3.3.5 If yes, what are the methods used to process and access personal data/sensitive information

Other

Due to the sensitive nature of the data, it is not publicly accessible.

Procurement Validation Dataset

The dataset consists of 30 procurement documents evaluated by CFCA experts. The procurement checklists prepared by the experts have been transformed into machine-readable form. For each procurement, 168 questions are asked regarding its compliance with legislation, and each question has an answer provided.

The dataset is divided into two subsets: a development dataset (10 procurements) and an evaluation dataset (20 procurements). The dataset consists of:

- 1) questions based on the checklist S.7.1.-PL-21 (09.12.2019 edition);
- 2) a labeled dataset corresponding to 30 procurements evaluated by CFCA.

Template: [LCS FARP](#)

Type: [Dataset](#)

1 Data Summary

1.1 Data Summary

1.1.1 What is the purpose of the data collection/generation?

The dataset was created to support the evaluation of automated procurement validation methods within the project. It contains procurement projects, relevant legislation, and reference annotations of procurement validation questionnaires associated with each project. The reference annotations (i.e., correct answers) were originally provided by the national authority, the Central Finance and Contracting Agency (CFCA), and subsequently transformed by the authors into a machine-readable format. This dataset directly contributes to the project objective of testing and improving AI-based approaches for procurement validation.

1.1.2 Type of data generated/collected

Textual data

1.1.3 Format of data generated/collected

- PDF
- Others

DOCX, YAML

1.1.4 Expected size of the data – give expected size and choose unit of measurement

12

MB

1.1.5 Are you re-using this data set?

No

1.1.6 If No, please describe, if you have considered re-using any of existing data?

Such a dataset was not available.

1.1.8 To whom the data might be useful ("data utility")? Other relevant remarks)

AI researchers

2 Research Data Management

2.1 Metadata and documentation

2.1.1 Will data be attributed with standard identification mechanism (e.g. persistent and unique identifiers such as Digital Object Identifiers – DOI)?

Yes

Handle

2.1.2 Do you plan to provide metadata for your data?

Yes

2.1.3 Will you use any metadata standard?

No

2.1.4 Will search keywords be provided that optimize possibilities for re-use?

No

2.1.5 Will you follow any naming conventions for keywords?

No

2.1.6 Will you provide clear version numbers?

Yes

2.2 Making data openly accessible

2.2.1 What type of access the data generated/produced will have (choose one)?

open (anyone is able to access data without restrictions)

2.2.2 Will you apply embargo period to access for your data?

No

2.2.3 Will data, associated metadata, documentation and code be made accessible with means of a repository?

Yes

CLARIN-LV repository

2.2.4 What methods or software tools are needed to access the data?

Python

2.2.5 Will documentation about the software needed to access the data included?

Yes

2.2.6 Is it possible to include the relevant software (e.g. in open source code)?

Yes

2.3 Making data interoperable

2.3.1 Are the formats open to software applications and to recombination with different data sets?

Yes

2.3.2 Will you use data standard vocabulary/taxonomy to make your data interoperable?

No

2.4 Increase data re-use

2.4.1 How will the data be licensed to permit the widest re-use possible? Indicate the license planned to use

CC BY-NC-SA 4.0

<https://creativecommons.org/licenses/by-nc-sa/4.0/>

2.4.2 Are the data usable by third parties, in particular after the end of the project?

Yes

2.4.3 When will the data be made available for re-use?

2025-08-27

2.4.5 Are data quality assurance processes provided?

No

3 Resources and Security

3.1 Allocation of resources

3.1.2 Who will be responsible for data management in your project?

Raivis Skadiņš (0000-0003-0929-2380)

3.3 Ethical aspects

3.3.1 Are there any ethical or legal issues that could have an impact on data collection and sharing?

No

3.3.2 Have you got/will you get permission from ethics committee to collect and process data (if applicable)?

No

3.3.3 Is informed consent for data sharing and long term preservation included in questionnaires dealing with personal data, if applicable?

No

3.3.4 Will data collected/generated include personal data/ sensitive information?

No

Embedding Model Fine-Tuning Dataset

For the purposes of this project, we fine-tuned the bge-m3 model developed by BAAI (Chen et al., 2024).

For fine-tuning, we collected DOCX procurement documents from the Electronic Procurement System (<https://www.eis.gov.lv/EKEIS/Supplier/>), allocating 7,083 files to the training set and 50 files to the validation set. The text from these documents was extracted and segmented. For each text segment, we used the OpenAI gpt-4o model to generate statements or questions whose correctness can be verified against that specific segment.

Template: [LCS FARP](#)

Type: [Dataset](#)

1 Data Summary

1.1 Data Summary

1.1.1 What is the purpose of the data collection/generation?

For fine-tuning the bge-m3 model developed by BAAI.

1.1.2 Type of data generated/collected

Machine-readable text

1.1.3 Format of data generated/collected

JSON

1.1.4 Expected size of the data – give expected size and choose unit of measurement

605

MB

1.1.5 Are you re-using this data set?

No

1.1.8 To whom the data might be useful ("data utility")? Other relevant remarks)

AI researchers

2 Research Data Management

2.1 Metadata and documentation

2.1.1 Will data be attributed with standard identification mechanism (e.g. persistent and unique identifiers such as Digital Object Identifiers – DOI)?

Yes

Handle

2.1.2 Do you plan to provide metadata for your data?

Yes

2.1.3 Will you use any metadata standard?

No

2.1.4 Will search keywords be provided that optimize possibilities for re-use?

No

2.1.5 Will you follow any naming conventions for keywords?

No

2.1.6 Will you provide clear version numbers?

Yes

2.2 Making data openly accessible

2.2.1 What type of access the data generated/produced will have (choose one)?

open (anyone is able to access data without restrictions)

2.2.2 Will you apply embargo period to access for your data?

No

2.2.3 Will data, associated metadata, documentation and code be made accessible with means of a repository?

Yes

CLARIN-LV repository

2.2.5 Will documentation about the software needed to access the data included?

No

2.2.6 Is it possible to include the relevant software (e.g. in open source code)?

No

2.3 Making data interoperable

2.3.1 Are the formats open to software applications and to recombination with different data sets?

No

2.3.2 Will you use data standard vocabulary/taxonomy to make your data interoperable?

No

2.4 Increase data re-use

2.4.1 How will the data be licensed to permit the widest re-use possible? Indicate the license planned to use

CC BY-NC-SA 4.0

<https://creativecommons.org/licenses/by-nc-sa/4.0/>

2.4.2 Are the data usable by third parties, in particular after the end of the project?

Yes

2.4.3 When will the data be made available for re-use?

2025-08-27

2.4.5 Are data quality assurance processes provided?

No

3 Resources and Security

3.1 Allocation of resources

3.1.2 Who will be responsible for data management in your project?

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3.3 Ethical aspects

3.3.1 Are there any ethical or legal issues that could have an impact on data collection and sharing?

No

3.3.2 Have you got/will you get permission from ethics committee to collect and process data (if applicable)?

No

3.3.3 Is informed consent for data sharing and long term preservation included in questionnaires dealing with personal data, if applicable?

No

3.3.4 Will data collected/generated include personal data/ sensitive information?

No

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